

Exploring Neuro-affirming Educational Practice to Support the Inclusion of Autistic Students: Insights from a Scoping Review and School Community Consultation

Carroll Keoghan

carroll.keoghan2@mail.dcu.ie

Recent shifts in national and international literature, policy and legislation reflect a move away from the historic deficit-based model of autism toward a rights-based, neurodiversity-informed perspective that recognises autism as a natural variation of human experience. The neurodiversity movement highlights the importance of including autistic voice in the development of practical neuro-affirming educational approaches. While there is growing recognition of the value of such practices in supporting the inclusion of autistic learners, there remains limited understanding of how they are implemented in everyday school settings. This initial phase of a doctoral research project aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of neuro-affirming practice and how it is enacted in schools. This paper outlines the proposed study design which includes a scoping review of existing literature, policy and official guidance followed by school community consultations, comprising of school leaders, teachers and support staff (additional needs assistants (ANAs)). Insights gathered will inform subsequent phases of the research project and have potential implications for educational policy and practice.

Keywords: autism, neuro-affirming practice, neuro-inclusive supports, inclusive educational practices, participatory research, autistic voice

Highlights

- Contemporary research, policy and official educational guidelines support the inclusion of neurodiversity-affirming practice. However, educational staff lack clear understanding and guidance on how these can be meaningfully enacted in everyday school life, highlighting a critical disconnect between theory and practice.
- Aligning with a neurodiversity and participatory lens, this study aims to examine the extent and nature of involvement of autistic individuals and school community members in the development of literature, policy and official guidance.
- This two-stage qualitative and participatory design seeks to explore how neuro-affirming educational practice is conceptualised, developed and enacted in school contexts through a scoping review of relevant literature and official guidance, followed by consultations with members of the school community. This approach will allow for the integration of policy and literature-based evidence with professional experience to ensure that the study's outcomes reflect existing knowledge and the perspectives of relevant stakeholders.

Introduction

This paper outlines the background and rationale for exploring the gap between recommended neuro-affirmative educational supports and how they are currently implemented in real world school contexts. It presents the justification for a two-stage methodological approach, followed by descriptions of how both will be conducted. Ethical considerations related to the inclusion of a consultation stages are addressed, and the paper concludes with reflections on how this initial study may inform subsequent phases of the doctoral research project and contribute to the evolving field of neuro-affirmative educational policy and practice.

Background

Over the last two decades, both international and national educational research, policy and legislation have reflected a significant shift from a medical, deficit-based understanding of autism toward a neurodiversity-informed model (Najeeb & Quadt, 2024; Wagland et al., 2025). This transition is grounded in rights-based principles shaped by the neurodiversity movement, legislative reforms such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2008) and evolving academic dialogue surrounding inclusive education.

Increasingly, educational research and policy reject historical deficit-based views of disability where autistic learners are expected to adapt to neurotypical norms and environments, to ‘fit in’ (Najeeb & Quadt, 2024; Pellicano & den Houting, 2022). Alternatively, the neurodiversity paradigm promotes inclusive approaches that recognise and value neurodiversity as a natural variation in human development, ‘adapt to fit me’. These neuro-affirming educational approaches emphasise autistic voice, autistic identity and autistic lived experience as being central to inclusive educational practice (Fletcher-Watson & Happe, 2019).

Research consistently highlights the diverse educational needs of autistic students, emphasising the importance of personalised, strengths-based and neuro-affirming teaching approaches (Ducarre, 2023; Goodall, 2018a; Roberts & Simpson, 2016). However, many educators report feeling ill-equipped to adapt their teaching methods to meet the diverse profiles of autistic learners (Roberts & Simpson, 2016). A lack of comprehensive professional development focused on neurodiversity and autism-specific evidenced informed practice continues to be identified as a significant barrier to inclusive education (Horgan,

Kenny & Flynn, 2023; Rice, Kenny & Connolly, 2023). Additionally, misunderstandings of autism among educational staff and absence of positive teacher-student relationships further hinder meaningful inclusion (Horgan, Kenny & Flynn, 2023; Mc Nally et al., 2025). These challenges highlight the ongoing disconnect between the inclusive, neuro-affirmative approaches advocated in contemporary literature and educational official guidance, and the realities of enacting them in everyday classroom practice.

Rationale

Despite the growing emphasis on the importance of neuro-affirming educational practice to support the inclusion of autistic students, its implementation in schools remain inconsistent (Pellicano & den Houting, 2022; Lynam et al., 2024; McNally et al., 2025). There is increasing research promoting the value of neuro-affirming educational approaches, however, a paucity of studies explores how these approaches are practically and meaningfully enacted within school contexts (Pellicano & den Houting, 2022; Wagland et al., 2025).

Research highlights that when educational professionals are meaningfully involved in shaping policy and practice, it leads to higher levels of adaptation in classrooms and helps to bridge the theory-practice gap (Goodall, 2018b; Roberts & Simpson, 2016). Correspondingly, contemporary studies emphasise the importance of developing neuro-affirming educational practices through an autism-informed lens, with autistic voices central to policy and guidance decision making (Fletcher-Watson et al., 2019; Pellicano & Heyworth, 2023).

Despite this, the key Irish educational guidance document, the Autism Good Practice Guidance for Schools-Supporting Children and Young People (Government of Ireland, 2022) contains deficit-based language and lacks meaningful inclusion of autistic individuals in its development (Lynam et al., 2024). To date, there remains limited understanding of how neuro-diversity-affirming practices can be operationalised effectively in schools, or how, if at all, members of school communities and autistic individuals have been involved in shaping guidance relating to neuro-affirming practice for schools.

Aims

Building on the rationale outlined, this initial study phase aims to explore the current landscape of this emerging educational field, investigate the policy-practice gap evident in current educational discourse and to deepen understanding of how neuro-affirmative practices can be meaningfully enacted in real-world school settings.

Phase One Aims

- To explore how neuro-affirming educational practice is defined and positioned to support the inclusion of autistic students.
- To investigate how, and to what extent, autistic individuals and school community members have been involved in the development of existing research, policy and guidance for neuro-affirming practice.
- To examine how and the extent to which neuro-affirming practices and guidance for supporting autistic students are being enacted within school settings.

These aims will be explored through the conduction of a scoping review followed by school community consultations involving school leaders, teachers and additional needs assistants.

1. *Scoping Review:*

- To identify and synthesis current national and international literature, policy and official guidance on neuro-affirming educational practice and examine how and to what extent autistic and school community voices have been included in their development.
- To identify key themes and gaps within academic and grey literature relating to neuro-affirmative educational practice to support the inclusion of autistic students

2. *School Community Consultations*

- To sense-check the findings from the scoping review and gather participants' perspectives on the relevance and applicability of these findings to school practice, including exploring participants' perceived facilitators and barriers to enacting neuro-affirming practice and identifying considerations not reflected in the literature.
- The consultation stage seeks to enhance the contextual relevance of the study, ensuring that outcomes are practically useful for school communities and accurately reflect stakeholders' professional experiences.
- To highlighting priorities or suggestions that may inform the focus and design of subsequent phases of the doctoral research project.

Research Questions

Shaped by the study's phase one aims, the following research questions will guide both the literature review and school community consultations.

1. How are neuro-diversity-affirming practices understood and enacted to support the inclusion of autistic students in schools?
2. How, and to what extent, have autistic individuals and school community members been included in the development of these practices?
3. What, if any, are the key opportunities and barriers for accessing, adopting and applying neuro-affirming educational approaches in real-world school settings?

In the following section the proposed methodological approach for this initial study phase will be discussed, including the rationale for the selected design, details of both the scoping review and school community consultations, and a description of key ethical considerations.

Methods

This initial study phase proposes to adopt a qualitative methodological approach involving a scoping review of literature followed by school community consultations, in response to both the emerging nature of the field and the limited research exploring how neuro-affirmative educational practices are enacted to support the inclusion of autistic learners.

Rationale

As a teacher educator with experience of supporting autistic learners my professional background informs my interest in neuro-affirming educational practice. The study is also shaped by Freirean and participatory research principles which highlight the importance of stakeholder voice and collaborative, actionable decision-making as keys to bridging the gap between policy and practice (Fletcher-Watson et al., 2019; Freire, 2017). I aim to adopt a reflexive stance throughout the study to ensure that participants' reflections and perspectives remain central to how I interpret their insights.

As there remains a significant gap between what is recommended in theory and what is implemented in practice, it is critical to map the existing national and international evidence base relating to the field of neuro-affirming practice. A scoping review will allow for a broad exploration of the current landscape of neuro-affirmative educational practice.

Aligning with the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) framework for conducting scoping reviews, and the author's own positionality this study will incorporate stakeholder consultations as the second part of the design. This proposes to ground the findings from the

literature review in knowledge users professional experience (Pollock et al., 2022). This two-part design aims not only to explore key themes and gaps in the literature base but also align with the values of neuro-diversity-affirming research by ensuring stakeholder participation is central from the outset of the research project.

Scoping Review

As neuro-diversity-affirming educational practice remains an emerging and evolving approach within the educational research field, a scoping review was identified as the most appropriate method to explore existing literature, policy and official guidance.

Purpose

The aim of the review is to develop a comprehensive understanding and identify gaps in knowledge regarding neuro-affirming practice, both of which will inform the subsequent phases of this research project. It will include a specific focus on exploring existing national and international literature, policy and official guidance documents. Additionally, the review will consider the extent to which autistic individuals and members of school communities have been meaningfully included within the development of relevant documentation. Finally, it aims to identify key themes relating to the opportunities and challenges to implementing neuro-affirmative practices in schools.

Review Protocol

The review's search strategy will be guided by a review protocol developed with the support of Dublin City University's subject librarian and guided by JBI Framework and The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis and Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) statement protocol (Tricco, 2018). The proposed protocol, which will be registered with Open Science Framework (OSF), will outline key decisions made relating to database selection, search terms, inclusion and exclusion criteria, selection of screening software and a description of the school community consultations.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

1. Inclusion Criteria

- Language: English language publications only, due to absence of translation funding.
- Date Range: 2010-2025: Reflects shifts following the lead up to diagnostic reclassification by the American Psychiatric Association, 201, in the DSM-5 and increased academic and policy interest in neurodiversity and inclusive education.

- Publication Type: Peer-reviewed empirical studies (all designs), systematic/scoping reviews, grey literature, including policy documents, frameworks and official guidelines related to neuro-affirming educational practice to support autistic students.
- Geographic Context: Publications from Ireland, UK, Europe (English speaking), USA, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand: Included due to similar educational and inclusion policies and English language publications.

2. Exclusion Criteria

- Language: Non-English publications.
- Date Range: Publications prior to 2010.
- Context: Studies conducted in non-school settings and non-mainstream school settings.
- Content Focus: Studies involving medical, deficit-based framing of autism.
- Age Group: Early childhood contexts and education beyond post-primary level.

Screening and Selection Process

The screening and selection of studies will be guided by the PRISMA-ScR framework to ensure transparency and replicability in the review process (Lely et al., 2023; Peters et al., 2020). All identified records will be imported in Covidence, a systematic review management tool, where duplicates will be removed automatically.

Titles and abstracts will be screened independently against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, followed by full text screening of eligible studies. To enhance rigour of the review process, a second independent reviewer will be involved in both the title/abstract and full text screening stages. Discrepancies will be discussed and resolved through consensus, and if needed, a third party will be consulted.

A PRISMA-ScR flow diagram will be created to visually represent the selection process, including the number of records identified, screened, excluded and included, along with reasons for exclusion at the full-text review stage. As this is an initial phase, the process is subject to refinement as the review progresses.

Data Extraction and Analysis

Data will be extracted using a structured data charting form developed in line with the JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis Guidelines (Pollock et al., 2023). Key information such as author(s), year, country, study design, population, focus of paper, neuro-affirmative

approaches discussed, and involvement of autistic individuals and or school community members will be recorded.

Extracted data will undergo descriptive analysis and inductive thematic analysis to identify patterns, gaps, opportunities and barriers regarding neuro-affirmative educational practices. A thematic analysis approach, following Braun and Clarke's six-phase method, will guide the coding and development of themes (2006). Analysis will focus on recurring concepts as well as contradictions between policy and practice. Findings from the review will directly inform the subsequent school community consultation stage.

School Community Consultations

This initial study phase is grounded in the principle of “nothing about us without us” recognising the importance of including stakeholders' voices within research, policy and practice development (Koontz et al., 2022). Both nationally and internationally, there has been a continued shift towards a rights-based, neurodiversity-informed perspective of autism. This approach values participatory research and emphasises the importance of including autistic voices in the design and implementation of educational interventions to ensure they meet the actual needs of students (Fletcher-Watson et al., 2014; Pellicano & Heyworth, 2023). Part two of the study's methodological approach involves engaging key stakeholders, namely autistic and non-autistic school community educational staff (outlined in Figure 1), to reflect on and discuss the review findings and how neuro-affirmative practices are currently understood and enacted in real-world school settings.

Purpose

The proposed consultations aim to gather perspectives and professional expertise from members of the school community to further contextualise the findings from the literature review. This process intends to contribute to a deeper understanding of how neuro-affirming real-world practices are experienced, not just confirming what is reflected within current literature. It seeks to examine whether the review findings align with their own professional experiences and identify any additional opportunities, barriers or gaps that may not have been captured in the literature. Engaging school community consultations aligns with the JBI framework for conducting scoping reviews, which positions stakeholder consultation, not as an optional phase, but as a key component of the research process (Pollock, 2022).

Participants

Neurodiverse consultation groups will be selected to ensure the process is not just participatory but aligns with a neurodiversity informed lens of including autistic voices within the research process. The consultation groups will comprise of autistic and non-autistic school leaders, teachers, support staff (additional needs assistants (ANAs)). The demographics of the school community consultations is further illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Outline of School Community Consultation Participants

The consultations will be conducted through a series of online, qualitative consultation sessions to encourage shared reflective discussion among participants. The online format was chosen to support accessibility and flexibility regarding communication and environment, aligning with a neuro-affirming approach. It also aims to enable participation from across Ireland, facilitating a broader geographical representation.

Data Collection and Analysis

Braun and Clarke's reflexive thematic approach will be used to explore participants' perspectives relating to the review findings. Analysis will involve an inductive six phase

process including data familiarisation, generation of initial codes, theme development, theme review, theme definition and report production (2006).

Consideration of Ethics

Stage Two of this study is categorised as low risk as it involves the voluntary participation of adult professionals. The consultations focus solely on participants' professional insights related to the findings of the scoping review. No personal or sensitive data will be collected. Standard ethical safeguards will be applied including informed consent, use of pseudonymisation and procedures for secure data storage and deletion. Participation is confidential and participants may withdraw at any stage prior to data analysis. These procedures align with Dublin City University's Faculty Research Ethics Committee (F-REC) requirements and full ethical approval will be obtained prior to the consultation recruitment stage.

Integration of Findings

An overview of the methodological approach to be undertaken in this study is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Outline of Methodological Approach

Figure 2 outlines the sequence of the study's methods from conducting the literature review to engaging in consultations, followed by integration of the findings from both. Integration of both methods will once again be guided by reflexive thematic analysis to ensure consistency throughout the methodology (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Finally, the proposed integration of findings from both components of this research design will provide a starting point for planning subsequent phases of the doctoral research project and outline implications for both the evolving design of the project and the wider field of neuro-affirmative education.

Implications

The proposed implications related to this novice researcher's study are outlined below in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Outline of Implications

Limitations

As this initial study is currently in its infancy, comprehensive limitations have not yet been addressed. However, the absence of autistic students' perspectives on the enactment of neuro-affirming practices to support their everyday schooling is a key limitation of this study phase. Aligning with the projects grounding in neuro-diversity informed research practice autistic student voice will be central to the subsequent phases of this doctoral research.

Conclusion

This paper has outlined the proposed initial study phase of a doctoral research project seeking to explore the evolving field of neuro-affirming practice to support the inclusion of autistic learners in schools. Preliminary literature searches identified that while research and policy promote the importance of including neuro-affirmative educational practices to support autistic students, limited knowledge exists regarding how school communities' access, apply and implement these approaches in real-world school environments. A scoping review of literature, policy and official guidance, followed by consultations with school community members seek to explore the developing landscape of neuro-affirming educational practice and the professional realities of enacting these practices to meaningfully support autistic students in real-world school settings.

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